

Dive into Trustworthy AI with two new courses

Every day, we rely on AI-made decisions. But how do we know which ones to trust? Discriminating, opaque, and vulnerable AI systems are a risk for their owners and users.

Given the evolving regulations in the EU, US, and China, it's crucial for every AI-using business to understand how to ensure its trustworthiness.

To tackle this demand, we co-created two courses on trustworthy AI on different skill levels: basic and advanced.

[Enroll now](#)

Enroll now and get a 20% discount

The contents of the course are accessible free of charge. If you'd like to solve exercises and earn a certificate from the course, we now offer the full course experience for 40€ (normally 50€). The price (per course) includes:

- Access to exercises
- Certificate upon completion

The offer is valid until October 31, 2023. VAT included where applicable.

[Get the discount](#)

This email was sent to spatial@autralis.org

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101021808. It reflects only author's view.

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